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Work Package	WP 4, Metadata and Ontologies
Lead Author (Org)	Parham Ramezani (LifeWatch ERIC), Nina Grau (INRAE), Clement Jonquet (INRAE), Nicola Fiore (LifeWatch ERIC)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Ilaria Rosati (CNR), Enrica Nestola (CNR), Maria Poveda-Villalon (UPM), Lucia Sanchez Gonzalez (UPM)
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Terminology

Acronym	Description
API / APIs	Application Programming Interface
BASF	Badische Anilin- und SodaFabrik
CO or CROP	Crop Ontology Project
CSP	Standing Committee on Science Priorities
DL	Description Logics
EFO	Experimental Factor Ontology
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EM	Engineering Methodologies
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable principle
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FOAF	Friend Of A Friend
GOMO	Governance Operational Model for Ontologies
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
IF	Interoperability Framework
IG / IGs	Interest Group
IILG	IUA-IVOA Liaison Committee
IRI	Internationalised Resource Identifier
IVOA	International Virtual Observatory Alliance
LOT	Linked Open Terms
MIRO	Minimum Information for the Reporting of an Ontology
NFDI	french National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and Environment
PID	Persistent Identifier
PURL	Persistent Uniform Resource Locator
OBO Foundry	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology Foundry
ODK	Ontology Development Kit
OMO	OBO Metadata Ontology
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RACI	Responsible, Accountable, Consulted and Informed responsibility assignment matrix
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDF-S	RDF Schema
SA / SAs	Semantic Artefact
SAC /SACs	Semantic Artefact Catalogue
SAREF	Smart Applications REference
SCSP	Standing Committee on Standards & Processes
SemVer	Semantic Versioning specification
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organisation System
SKOSMOS	Open source web-based SKOS vocabulary
SOPs	Standard Operating Procedures
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SPOT	Samples, Phenotypes and Ontology Team
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
TCG	Technical Coordination Group
TG / TGs	Task Group
UMLS	Unified Medical Language System
UUID / UUIDs	Universally Unique Identifier
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WG /WGs	Working Group
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

Semantic artefacts (SAs - ontologies, terminologies, taxonomies, thesauri, vocabularies, metadata schemas and standards) are essential for standardising data representation and annotation, encapsulating the highest level of meaningful knowledge within interoperability frameworks. These artefacts are fundamental to sustainable, quality-verified data practices, aligning with the FAIR Data Principles, particularly Principle I.2. Although experts, including those in the EOSC Interoperability Framework, emphasise the need for governance policies for SA, no universal governance model exists that fits all scientific communities or projects. This deliverable presents several governance models to guide and inspire stakeholders in addressing the governance of semantic artefacts. It is the final and primary deliverable (D4.1) of FAIR-IMPACT's T4.1 on "Semantic artefact disciplinary governance," which reviews and analyses community practices to propose strategies tailored to SAs' characteristics.

This document sets out the baseline modality of semantic artefact governance derived from surveyed community-based practices. It provides actionable models for communities or institutions looking to establish or update their semantic artefact governance frameworks. The report is structured into four main sections. The first section introduces the overarching context and the inherent challenges of SA governance, setting the stage for understanding the complexities involved. The second section delves into the three primary components derived from community-based practices: engineering methodologies, organisational structure, and governance framework. Engineering methodologies cover the technical processes and lifecycle management of SAs. The organisational structure addresses the roles and responsibilities within institutions that support effective governance, and the governance framework outlines the high-level principles and standards guiding SA governance. The third section outlines the methodology used to develop the governance models, detailing the steps taken to synthesise community practices into structured, applicable models. The final section presents these models which address the diverse needs of different scientific communities and projects.

As a result of this comprehensive analysis, FAIR-IMPACT T4.1 has formulated initial requirements and developed three distinct models of semantic artefact governance based on community-based stewardship practices. These models facilitate synchronicity, promoting coordinated efforts across scientific communities and ensuring consistent application of best practices. They aim to ensure long-term sustainability by supporting the enduring use and maintenance of semantic artefacts and aiding EOSC communities in integrating semantic artefacts within the European Open Science Cloud, thus advancing the FAIR data agenda. This deliverable empowers stakeholders with the tools and frameworks to establish robust governance structures for semantic artefacts, fostering a more interconnected and sustainable data ecosystem.

1. Introduction

1.1 Topic presentation

1.1.1 Context

Currently, data sharing is actively promoted by policy making bodies such as the European Commission¹, supported by evidence that increased data sharing generally fosters innovation. Semantic Artefacts (SAs) are employed to represent and annotate data in a standardised manner. For this work, we have adopted the definition of SA provided by the FAIRsFAIR project and embraced it FAIR-IMPACT: *“a machine-actionable and -readable formalisation of a conceptualisation enabling sharing and reuse by humans and machines”*². In other words, we use the term SA as a broader term to include ontologies, terminologies, taxonomies, thesauri, vocabularies, metadata schemas, and standards. SAs embody the highest level of meaningful knowledge representation within an interoperability framework, making them particularly sensitive to changes, versioning, sharing, management, etc., all governance-related aspects.

The governance of SA has been identified as a requirement by the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Interoperability Framework (IF) and the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) (v1)³:

- *“SRIA: Develop governance structures for coordinating the work on metadata and ontologies within EOSC, both for specific disciplinary communities and overall coordination.*
- *SRIA: This governance should be built primarily around existing discipline-based communities but needs to be coordinated across these communities within EOSC*
- *SRIA: The work that these governance structures coordinate should include registries that describe metadata schemata in a standardised and machine-actionable way, better researcher-focused tools and services working with these metadata, crosswalks between existing metadata schemata, and training and documentation.*
- *IF: Repositories of semantic artefacts rules with a clear governance framework.*
- *IF: Documents explaining terms and conditions and acceptable use policies for interoperability services are needed. For instance, providing clear descriptions of the service-level agreements of those providing catalogues and registries of semantic artefacts.”*

FAIR-IMPACT T4.1 was created to address these requirements when deploying EOSC.

¹ <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1024/oj>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4314320>

³ <https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/SRIA-1.0.pdf>

1.1.2 Challenges

SA has become central to sustainable, quality-verified data recommendations to preserve their integrity, such as the FAIR Principles⁴. However, the FAIR Principles include a notion of “long-term care,” expert groups advocate for establishing governance policies for these dynamic entities. Despite the acknowledged importance of governance for SA, there is no standard definition for SA governance available in the literature, underscoring the complexity of this task. Indeed, governance comprises the framework through which an organisation is directed and managed, including the procedures ensuring accountability for the entity and its members. It involves the processes of decision making, establishing rules, and implementing enforcement mechanisms to steer the operations of an organisation or community. Given its broad applicability across various domains, governance is often combined with specific contexts, leading to terms such as metadata governance, service governance, project governance, etc. Despite the various formats the term encompasses, governance aims to enhance efficiency, objectivity, and transparency in an organisation's structures and decision-making processes.

1.1.3 FAIR-IMPACT project and T4.1 goals

The FAIR-IMPACT project supports harmonising and synchronising the FAIR Principles and practices to realise a FAIR EOSC environment. FAIR-IMPACT recognises the critical role of governance in sustaining FAIR research outputs and services, dedicating a specific task to this subject with a focus on SAs. FAIR-IMPACT's T4.1, entitled “Semantic artefact disciplinary governance”, seeks to review and analyse community governance practices for SAs and to develop governance models. By doing so, T4.1 advances expert recommendations by providing models for SA governance. Community-based stewardship practices in SA governance will facilitate synchronicity across scientific communities and ensure long-term sustainability.

1.2. Objectives of the T4.1 deliverable (D4.1)

1.2.1. Scope of the D4.1

This deliverable aims to: (1) identify governance modalities for SAs and (2) provide governance models applicable in various disciplines for making relevant SA-related decisions with the appropriate stakeholders. To achieve this, the approach involves comparing and analysing existing SA governance practices within various communities connected to EOSC.

During a workshop held in September 2023⁵, we invited esteemed speakers from various exemplary communities who contributed to elucidating SA governance models. We have compiled nine exemplary cases of governance practices about SAs. A Milestone entitled

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁵ “Semantic artefact workshop”, webpage of the FAIR-IMPACT event. 2023. URL : <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-impact-semantic-artefact-governance-workshop>

MS4.1: "Semantic Artefact Governance Models: Examples of Community Practices"⁶, has been produced to report the communities surveyed and the multiple approaches to community-driven governance of SAs examined during this workshop, serving as the baseline for the final deliverable of governance models for SAs within the EOSC in Deliverable 4.1 (D4.1).

This document considers SAs specifically utilising semantic web technologies and standards within their development processes. Consequently, the deliverable's output, which comprises potential SA governance models, is aligned with Semantic Web practices.

1.2.2 Methodology

The first step adopts a bottom-up approach to capture the actual practices employed by various communities in managing their SAs. Insights were gathered through the "FAIR-IMPACT Semantic Artefact Governance Workshop," where diverse governance strategies and practices were explored across multiple communities. Secondly, we employed a top-down approach to define SA governance by adapting existing definitions of data governance from the literature to the critical components of SAs. This dual approach integrates the functions and concepts of SA governance, allowing us to identify key components and develop recommendations closely aligned with observed standard practices. To achieve this, we focused on incorporating practical elements of SA governance, taken from the bottom-up approach, into the SA governance components derived from the top-down approach, ensuring that the governance models reflect both theory and actual community practices.

1.2.3 Semantic Artefact governance definition

Governance of development and maintenance practices is essential for establishing a network of interoperable SAs within an organization or community, ensuring that these efforts do not result in siloed data. Several initiatives have set high-level operational rules to measure the interoperability of created SAs through dedicated tests or assessment metrics. These initiatives aim to integrate the rules into a structured methodology necessary for the management of SAs. At the same time, recognizing clear accountabilities for these assets and responsibilities for related processes has a significant impact on effective governance. Some initiatives prioritize adapting existing principles and practices to maintain broad aspects of interoperability. However, adopting these strategies is not always straightforward, as their implementation can vary widely depending on the technologies in use, organizational structures, or specific goals. As a first step to address this issue, we aim to provide a generic definition that is broadly applicable across different contexts. This definition builds on existing works, including insights from communities of practice and data governance definitions derived from a structured literature review presented by René Abraham et al. 2019⁷. We formalised the semantic artefact governance and management as:

⁶ "MS4.1. Semantic artefact models: examples of community practices". 2023 T4.1 milestone report DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10287010](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10287010)

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.07.008>

A principled approach for regulating various aspects of semantic artefact lifecycle, from acquisition through usage to deprecation. Semantic artefact governance establishes policies, standards, procedures, and monitors compliance. It defines decision-making, accountabilities, roles, and responsibilities about these assets.

Thus, we broke down SA governance into: 1) Engineering Methodology, 2) Organisational Structure and 3) Governance Framework, which will be scrutinised for all the surveyed organisations and communities. This separation allowed us to categorise practices for SA development and management that align with the features of each component. These components are then modular to form SA governance models for several target groups.

2. Semantic artefact governance components

The SA governance definition allowed us to identify three main components:

(1) **Engineering Methodology** (EM) comprises processes, methods, and tools for building SAs. Despite various classifications of EMs, they share the commonality of structuring activities, tasks, and operations into systematic and formal phases necessary for developing SAs such as conceptualization, encoding, publication and maintenance. In FAIR-IMPACT, T4.2 and T5.3 investigate the development of a FAIR-by-design methodology.

(2) **Organisational Structure** outlines how specific activities are allocated and directed to achieve the organisation’s goals. It defines decision-making, accountabilities, roles, responsibilities, and the engagement of stakeholders. Operational mechanisms, such as Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), can be employed to disseminate tasks among actors.

(3) **Governance Framework** defines a set of high-level rules and agreed-upon specifications to provide mechanisms for management, supports the development, maintenance, and use of standard tools, and facilitates the application of best practices.

2.1. Engineering Methodology

The Engineering Methodology (EM) acts as a backbone for implementing governance methods. SA EM, or with a narrower focus, such as in the case of Ontology EM, primarily fall under SA management due to its emphasis on practical implementation and operational aspects of creating, maintaining, and evolving SAs. However, to integrate the governance and management of SAs, a methodological approach to SA engineering has been included as an SA governance component. Further details are referenced in FAIR-IMPACT’s T4.2.1, which produced a revised Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology (“Processes & tools to engineer FAIR semantic artefacts” T4.2 milestone report)⁸.

The EM varies depending on the type of SAs under development, the strategy which would be either building them from scratch or reusing existing SA, the associate domain, and the maturity level of infrastructure, data, tools, and processes in SA management. We illustrate

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10551054>

the diversity by showcasing Initiatives' decisions to either develop their own methods, specific workflows and related tools internally, customise all steps of SA lifecycle based on their requirements and objectives, or adapt existing EMs to adhere to best practices and increase interoperability with others in terms of SA development and management processes.

Figure 1. Schema of the workflow between users, curators and technical coordinators within the Crop Ontology project.⁹

The **Crop Ontology project** is one of the initiatives that has developed its own methodology for creating crop-specific trait knowledge graphs based on a semantic domain model. They have established workflows for mapping structured data (CSV and Excel files) to graphs with respect to the Crop Ontology terms and publish them on a searchable library¹⁰. Quality and validation checker tools and submission processes are embedded in the workflows to semi-automate the development process. Fig. 1 represents the roles and workflow for creating crop-specific graphs and submitting new terms to these graphs.

⁹ <https://hdl.handle.net/10568/118001>

¹⁰ <https://cropontology.org/>

Figure 2. Linked Open Terms (LOT) Methodology.¹¹

In contrast, the **BASF** organisation has adopted the LOT methodology¹² (Fig. 2), a lightweight methodology for developing ontologies and vocabularies. The LOT methodology defines iterations over a basic workflow composed of the following activities: ontological requirements specification, ontology implementation, ontology publication, and Ontology maintenance. This methodology emphasises compatibility with software development techniques, increases reusability, and focuses on publication and online ontology.

Another example of an initiative using its own strategies to address EM is the Smart Applications REFERENCE (**SAREF**) set of ontologies developed by ETSI. They have defined a project-oriented workflow (Fig. 3 & 4) to create new versions of the SAREF ontology and its extensions. Instead of focusing on specific sequential phases of ontology development, they have designed a workflow articulated around the use of issues in the corresponding SAREF project issue tracker on the ETSI public forge¹³, as it “enables not only to have a single point of interaction for development but also to keep track of the development activity and discussions”¹³.

¹¹ <https://lot.linkeddata.es/>

¹² <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2022.104755>

Figure 3. Different states of a new SAREF project version proposal and the transitions among them.¹³

Figure 4 Different states of SAREF project version development and the transitions among them.¹³

In the biological and biomedical domain, one of the most prominent initiatives, **OBO Foundry**, promotes a practical approach by offering centralised infrastructure through the Ontology Development Kit¹⁴ for managing the ontology lifecycle. It comprises two architectural components:

- A toolbox containing all the necessary tools for ontology development, from Unix command-line tools like rsync and git to specialised ontology pipeline programs like ROBOT. The ROBOT source code consists of 'robot-core' and 'robot-command'.
 - 'robot-core' is a library supporting everyday ontology development tasks, referred to as "operations" (such as Convert, Reasoning, Extract, Query, Report, etc.).
 - 'robot-command' provides a command-line interface divided into "commands", each of which wraps a 'robot-core' operation.

¹³ https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/103600_103699/103673/01.01.01_60/ts_103673v010101p.pdf

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/baac087>

- A set of executable ontology-engineering workflows delivered as a directory of scripts, build rules, and source files. Examples of these workflows include initialisation and update workflows, editors' workflows, quality control and continuous integration workflows, release workflows, and workflows for importing and reusing existing ontologies.

However, in many communities of practice, initiatives do not explicitly follow or establish a specific EM. Within our reviewed communities, the **Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)**, the owner of **AGROVOC** and **INRAE**, the owner of **INRAE Thesaurus**, approach the SA development and curation by leveraging common editorial platforms (e.g., VocBench¹⁵ and Protégé¹⁶) to enable collaborative SA management. Development groups usually schedule regular updates and releases continuously. The SAs result from these processes is generally deployed in systems like SKOSMOS¹⁷ and ShowVoc¹⁸ or published in SA catalogues (SAC) (e.g., AgroPortal¹⁹, EcoPortal²⁰, etc.) to ensure the accessibility and long-term preservation of resources. In other cases, in addition to the previous strategy by FAO and INRAE, initiatives develop extra tools in a workflow manner to address a particular part of the SA lifecycle. For example, **EMBL-EBI**, as an owner of **the Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO)**, created workflows for receiving new term requests and implementing term changes. Another example is **NFDI4Biodiv**, which designs standard pipelines to transform taxonomies into OWL products.

Organisations like the **International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA)**, which deals with weak semantic types (e.g., controlled lists and schemas), employ document-oriented processes to build consensus within the community around virtual observatory technology. IVOA working drafts become recommendations by following this process. Fig. 5 shows the labels that describe increasing levels of maturity and consensus in the standards process.

Figure 5. IVOA document promotion process.²¹

¹⁵ <https://vocbench.uniroma2.it/>

¹⁶ <https://protege.stanford.edu/>

¹⁷ <https://skosmos.org/>

¹⁸ <https://showvoc.uniroma2.it/>

¹⁹ <https://agroportal.lirmm.fr/>

²⁰ <https://ecoportal.lifewatch.eu/>

²¹ <https://www.ivoa.net/documents/DocStd/20170517/>

2.2. Organisational Structure

This section focuses on characterising the Organisational Structure component of SA governance. We will explore and identify (1) the stakeholders organisation involved in the decision-making process, (2) the framework of decision types and accountabilities associated with SA governance, and (3) the operational mechanisms for disseminating decisions among various stakeholders.

All the resources collected and used for the organisational structure analysis are listed in the “Appendices” section. Each appendix contains data for three communities, covering the accessibility of governance documents, their sources, the organisation of formal stakeholder groups (including their presence and names), and the identification and descriptions of stakeholders' roles and responsibilities, either as groups or individuals, as detailed in the documents. For convenience, the appendices have been split into three part: Appendix A for the Crop Ontology project (CROP), OBO Foundry and BASF, appendix B for INRAE Vocabularies, IVOA and NFDI4Biodiv, and appendix C for EMBL-EBI, SAREF and AGROVOC communities. Although additional resources are available online, only the descriptions collected for BASF (Appendix B) and EMBL-EBI (Appendix C) are limited to the actors' names assigned to their activities. This means that most of the communities surveyed (7 out of 9) provide substantial information on their stakeholders' roles and accountabilities, allowing for a representative analysis.

The first analysis lies in defining the distribution of roles and tasks among stakeholders. To achieve this, we distribute the stakeholders of each community, collected in Appendixes A, B, and C, according to their affiliation, either to a group or to a single individual of actors associated with a specific activity ([Table 1](#)).

Table 1. Distribution of stakeholders of each community based on their affiliation to a specific group or an individual activity. Italic is used to represent the stakeholders' names assigned by each community, and underlines represent each group name.

Community	Groups	Individuals
CROP	- <u>Committees</u> : <i>Curators Committee; Strategy Committee; Scientific Advisory Committee</i> - <u>Team</u> : <i>CO team (Technical and Ontology coordinators)</i>	<i>CO management institute</i>
OBO Foundry	- <u>Committees</u> : <i>Operations Committee (3 working groups); Code of Conduct Committee</i> - <u>Working groups (WG)</u> : <i>Editorial WG; Technical WG; Outreach WG</i>	-
BASF	- <u>Team</u> : <i>Data semantic team</i>	<i>Ontology developer; Ontology owner; Ontology curator; Domain Expert; End-user</i>
INRAE Voc	- <u>Committees</u> : <i>Editorial Committee</i> - <u>Groups</u> : <i>Tasks groups (TGs)</i>	<i>SA authors, External experts</i>
IVOA	- <u>Committees</u> : <i>Executive Committee; Standing Committee on Science Priorities (CSP); Standing Committee on Standards & Processes (SCSP); IUA-IVOA Liaison Committee (IILG)</i> - <u>Groups</u> : <i>Technical Coordination Group (TCG); Working groups (WGs); Interest group (IGs); Media Group</i>	-

NFDI4Biodiv	- <u>Committee</u> : Taxonomies Editorial Committee - <u>Board</u> : Taxonomies Editorial Board - <u>Groups</u> : Tasks groups	Ontology managers, Experts in the biodiversity domain
EMBL-EBI	- <u>Team</u> : Samples, phenotypes and ontology (SPOT) team: -Ontology Application team -Semantic data integration service team	Project leaders; Managers; Coordinators; Editors; Developers; Curators; Data engineers
SAREF	- <u>Committee</u> : ETSI SmartM2M Technical Committee - <u>Board</u> : Steering Board members; Technical Board members	Project leader; Ontology developer; Contributor; Ontology user
AGROVOC	- <u>Board</u> : Core Board - <u>Team</u> : AGROVOC team	Manager; Curator; Technical lead; Technical support; Communication support; Editors, Development, Curators; Experts

OBO Foundry and **IWOA** are the only two surveyed communities that have entirely centralised their stakeholder activities within formal groups. A significant proportion of the communities (5 out of 9) have adopted a mixed stakeholder organisation, consisting of formal groups of authorities and individuals assigned specific tasks. This is the case for **CROP**, **INRAE Voc**, **NFDI4Biodiv** and **AGROVOC**. For **BASF** and **EMBL-EBI** communities, we have yet to find a formal organisation of the stakeholders involved in the SA governance. **BASF** and **EMBL-EBI** are considered task-centred communities. Indeed, while a “*Data semantic team*” exists within **BASF**, stakeholders' roles are distributed according to individual responsibilities, such as the ontology owner, developers, ontology curator, domain expert, and end-user. Although the EMBL-EBI institute has a team called “Samples, Phenotypes and Ontology (SPOT)”, which is further divided into two sub-teams, the activities depend on the service provided; these activities do not appear to be related to specific stakeholder responsibilities.

Thus, we identified six types of formal groups: Committees, Boards, Teams, Working groups (WGs), Interest groups (IGs), and Task Groups (TGs). Additionally, we categorised eight individual task activities assigned to specific actions, including domain expertise, management, coordination, project investigation, ontology development, curation, use, and contribution. While, the names assigned either to the stakeholder groups or to the individual task are highly heterogeneous depending on the communities, we can deduce that the establishment of a structured framework for a cohort of stakeholders engaged in SA governance appears important, given that nearly all communities have organised their stakeholders within at least one formal group, and supplement them with specific task assignments which mainly involve specific SA activities and coordination.

The second subcomponent of the Organisational Structure in SA governance outlines the broad spectrum of accountabilities assigned to stakeholders. Understanding this subcomponent necessitates examining the responsibilities defined within each formal group or individual stakeholder. Indeed, Table 1 demonstrates that diverse designations exist within the same formal group that do not clarify specific accountabilities. This underscores the importance of delineating decisions and responsibilities assigned to each structured group and individual task. To address this issue, we identified and compiled stakeholders' responsibilities by domain of activity (Appendix D).

A domain of activity is defined when the same task or responsibility is observed in at least two communities. Thus, we identified eight domains of activity in SA governance:

Editorial: Focuses on developing, maintaining, and updating the principles and standards of the initiative. This includes creating, implementing, and overseeing review processes for these principles and standards, as well as establishing policies that ensure editorial consistency and quality control.

Technical: Responsible for the upkeep and administration of the technical infrastructure. This includes managing websites, repositories, APIs, SPARQL endpoints, and other related services and workflows, ensuring they are up-to-date, secure, and accessible.

Outreach: Manages the organisation's public relations and external communications. This includes monitoring communication channels, producing documentation and educational resources, and representing the organisation at events and other external venues to enhance engagement and awareness.

Coordination (Project management): Oversees the consistency and alignment of governance policies and standards, ensuring technical compliance. This area supports best practices and coordinates training for curators, fostering collaborative interactions between teams to reinforce policy coherence.

SA Development: Encompasses the full lifecycle of developing and releasing SAs, from initial conception to final deployment. This includes iterative development processes, version management, and ensuring that artefacts are released with documentation and clear functionality for end users.

SA Curation: Ensures that SAs are current and aligned with ongoing requirements. This includes managing technical lifecycle aspects like versioning, deprecation, and identification, while also engaging with the community, expert networks, and external entities to maintain semantic compliance and foster collaboration.

Expertise: An advisory group of subject-matter experts providing specialised knowledge to support ontology validation and accuracy. This team promotes and guides the use of SAs, offering recommendations for content evolution, reuse, and adaptation while validating changes and improvements.

Community: Foster an inclusive, collaborative network of stakeholders involved in the development, use, and governance of semantic artefacts. This involves engaging owners, users, curators, and contributors, feedback loops, and communication channels.

Almost all communities (8 out of 9), except for **BASF**, provide detailed descriptions of stakeholders' responsibilities in editorial activities. While this activity is always organised among stakeholders, only **EMBL-EBI** assigns individual stakeholders to this role. Expertise activity oversight is provided either by external actors, as in the cases of **INRAE Voc** and **AGROVOC**, or by dedicated groups within the community, such as in **CROP**, **IVOA**, **NFDI4Biodiv**, and **EMBL-EBI**. For **BASF** and **SAREF**, the existence of this stakeholder role is confirmed, but no further details are available. For outreach, **OBO Foundry**, **IVOA**, and **AGROVOC** have dedicated groups for this task. In contrast, **CROP** manages this responsibility by a non-specific group already assigned to other activity domains. Coordination activity is broadly shared among the surveyed communities (7 out of 9). While **CROP**, **IVOA**, and **NFDI4Biodiv** have formally involved specific groups of stakeholders in this activity, only

EMBL-EBI assigns this role to individual actors. Coordination can also be managed by stakeholders involved in other activities, as seen in the **OBO Foundry**, **IVOA**, **SAREF**, and **AGROVOC** communities. For technical activities, the **CROP**, **OBO Foundry**, **SAREF**, and **AGROVOC** communities involve groups of stakeholders. Conversely, **BASF** and **EMBL-EBI** engage individual stakeholders or multiple actors in these tasks. Project management is present in 6 out of 9 communities (**CROP**, **BASF**, **INRAE Voc**, **EMBL-EBI**, **SAREF**, **AGROVOC**). It is primarily fulfilled by SA authors or owners who are part of the community's stakeholders. Finally, the last two domains of activity are SA curation and SA development: Curation is explicitly specified by four of the nine communities (**CROP**, **BASF**, **EMBL-EBI**, **AGROVOC**) and usually requires expert opinions for **INRAE Voc**, **NFDI4Biodiv**, **SAREF**, and **AGROVOC** communities. Development activities can be assigned to specific individual actors, such as **BASF**, **EMBL-EBI**, **SAREF**, and **NFDI4Biodiv**. However, in **CROP**, **OBO Foundry**, **INRAE Voc**, **IVOA**, and **AGROVOC**, this activity is mainly assigned to stakeholders already involved in other domains of activity.

To summarise, we identified eight domains of activity involved in SA governance, which enabled us to design the SA governance framework. The significance of each domain can be assessed by the number of communities that have assigned stakeholders to manage each activity (see Box 1 below).

Box 1. Classification of activity domains based on the number of times they have been incorporated into the SA governance process for each interviewed community..

- 1-SA development** (9) (CROP; OBO Foundry; BASF; INRAE Voc, IVOA, NFDI4Biodiv; EMBL-EBI, SAREF, AGROVOC)
- 2-SA curation** (8) (CROP, OBO Foundry; BASF; INRAE Voc; EMBL-EBI; SAREF; AGROVOC)
- 3-Editorial** (8) (CROP, OBO Foundry, INRAE Voc, IVOA, NFDI4Biodiv, EMBL-EBI, AGROVOC)
- 4-Expertise** (8) (CROP; BASF; INRAE Voc, IVOA; NFDI4Biodiv; EMBL-EBI; SAREF; AGROVOC)
- 5-Coordination** (7) (CROP; OBO Foundry; IVOA; NFDI4Biodiv; EMBL-EBI; SAREF; AGROVOC)
- 6-Project management** (6) (CROP; BASF; SA authors; EMBL-EBI; SAREF; AGROVOC)
- 7-Technical** (6) (CROP, OBO Foundry, BASF; EMBL-EBI; SAREF; AGROVOC)
- 8-Outreach** (4) (CROP; OBO Foundry; BASF; IVOA)

To finalise our analysis of the Organisational Structure of stakeholders involved in SA governance, we examine how information is disseminated among different actors to ensure effective decision implementation. To achieve this, we categorise the actors by their domains of responsibility (Table 2):

- Decision making, defined as the responsibility being of to establishing best practices to ensure policy accuracy ;
- Executive processes, defined as the responsibility to carry out the tasks and inputs for the effective management and implementation of the SA;
- Orchestration defined as the responsibility to ensure the effective compliance between the policy rules and their implementation. Typically, orchestration comes into the picture to verify the correctness of the execution processes.

Table 2. Distribution of stakeholder names assigned by each community according to their roles in decision making, executive processes and orchestration. * identify stakeholders who do not have descriptions of their accountabilities

Domain of responsibility Communities surveyed	Decision making	Executive processes		Orchestration	
	Editorial	SA curation	SA development	Coordination	Procedures
CROP	Strategy committee; Scientific committee	Curator committee; Ontology coordinator	CO team	CO team (Technical and ontology coordinator)	-
OBO Foundry	Editorial Committee	Technical WG	Technical WG	Technical WG; Editorial WG	Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)
BASF*	-	Ontology curators*	Developers*	-	RACI
INRAE Voc	Editorial Committee	Editorial committee; experts	Editorial Committee	-	-
IVOA	WGs; IGs; Executive committee	-	TCG	Executive committee; TCG; SCSP committee	Technical specifications
NFDI4Biodiv	Tasks groups: Taxonomies editorial board	Experts	Ontology manager	Taxonomies editorial committees	-
EMBL-EBI*	Ontology editorial lead*	Curators*	Ontology developers; semantic data engineer*	Coordinators (Catalog; ontology project coordinator)*	-
SAREF	ETSI SmartM2M Technical Committee	Steering board members	Project lead; ontology developer	Ontology developer; Steering board members	Technical specifications
AGROVOC	Core board	Agrovoc team (curator); experts	Editors: AGROVOC team (Technical support and manager)	Core board	Editorial guidelines; Semantic data interoperability

For **NFDI4Biodiv** and **EMBL-EBI**, stakeholders are divided into three distinct roles, with specific actors or groups involved in decision making, executive processes, or orchestration. In **CROP** and **SAREF**, a particular group of stakeholders handles decision making, while a shared group manages executive processes and orchestration roles. For **OBO Foundry** and **IVOA**, actors involved in decision making also participate in orchestration activities, while those responsible for orchestration are as well involved in executive processes. **AGROVOC** has a similar organisation, except that executive responsibilities are specifically assigned. **INRAE Voc** is the only community where stakeholders are involved in both decision making and executive processes. Finally, we found that 4 out of 9 communities have formal procedures that precisely describe the execution process, as seen in **OBO Foundry**, **IVOA**, **SAREF**, and **AGROVOC**. **BASF** has only defined roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders using the RACI (Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, and Informed) responsibility assignment matrix.

To summarise this third component of the Organisational structure of SA governance , we found that CROP, NFDI4Biodiv, EMBL-EBI, and SAREF have decentralised roles and

responsibilities, with stakeholders involved only in decision-making. In contrast, INRAE Voc, OBO Foundry, IVOA, and AGROVOC centralise decision-makers who also hold other responsibilities, facilitating the orchestration and implementation of policies and guidelines, but are also usually supplemented by formal procedure documents such as SOPs or technical procedures.

2.3. Governance Framework

The **Governance Framework** is the third component of our approach to SA governance; it provides mechanisms for management by establishing high-level rules and standards. In the following paragraphs, we examine the governance practices of the communities surveyed.

As one of the leading organisations in governance and management of ontologies in the biological and biomedical domain, OBO Foundry provides principles²² for integrating and harmonising open and FAIR ontologies. Fifteen principles have been defined, outlining recommendations, best practices, and standards for developing and reusing ontologies. “Originally, these principles were not precisely formulated, and interpretation was subjective. Consequently, they have been formally encoded as operational rules to enable the establishment of automated validation checks”.²³ The OBO Dashboard²⁴ (Fig. 6) has been developed to utilise these operational rules to provide a set of automated tests that guarantee a minimum level of compliance with OBO Principles and best practices. Through this approach, OBO Foundry has been structured and assessed based on criteria that help to improve overall quality and interoperability, which is crucial for making data FAIR.

Ontology (click for details)	Open	Format	URIs	Versioning	Scope	Definitions	Relations	Documented	Users	Authority	Naming	Maintained	Responsible	ROBOT Report
apollo_sv	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠	?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠
cl	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠	?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠
disdriv	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠
doid	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠	?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠
dpo	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠	?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠
eco	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠
envo	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠	?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠
fbcv	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠	?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠
fbdv	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
go	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠	?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠
hancestro	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠	?	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	⚠

Figure 6. A fundamental analysis provided by the OBO Foundry dashboard, the left column lists the ontologies under the test, and each row represents the result of the test for each ontology concerning OBO principles.²⁰

²² <https://obofoundry.org/principles/fp-000-summary.html>

²³ <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/baab069>

²⁴ <https://dashboard.obofoundry.org/>

The need for a holistic approach to ontology governance has led **BASF company** to create a Governance Operational Model (GOMO)²⁵ for BASF ontologies, which offers a framework to coordinate and control the development, management, and curation of ontologies throughout the stages of the ontology lifecycle. GOMO consists of four main components: principles, standards and associate quality assurance method, along with best practices, training and outreach (Fig. 7). It results from a collaborative effort between industry and academia in the semantic web field, integrating concepts from data governance, schema.org, and the OBO and IOF Foundries.

Figure 7. GOMO components and interlinked interactions²⁵

The following definitions of components have been extracted from the paper presenting GOMO:

- **“Governance principles** define a set of high-level fundamental rules on how the organisation should develop, publish, maintain, and consume ontologies.
- **Standards** are a set of agreed-upon specifications to be followed during the ontology lifecycle. Each standard is associated with a **quality assurance** method that allows human—or software-based evaluation of its correct implementation.
- **Best Practices** Comprise is a set of recommendations and guidelines that explain and illustrate how to follow the principles and implement the standards while providing the user with the background knowledge required to perform specific activities.
- **Training and outreach** Comprise a series of interactive, expert-led workshops to explain the concepts and guidelines from best practices and standards with tailored examples for the target audience.”

BASF currently has defined seven principles for ontology governance, including 1. Fairness, 2. Availability, 3. Access Rights and Security Policy, 4. Persistency, 5. Documentation, 6. Modularity, and 7. Community.

²⁵<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7007495>

SAREF also provided four principles²⁶: 1. reuse and alignment, 2. modularity, 3. extensibility, and 4. maintainability. These principles are dedicated to the design of the SAREF core ontology and its different extensions.

However, many initiatives have yet to define principles explicitly. Organisations like INRAE, EMBL-EBI, and NFDI4Biodiv have aligned their governance approaches with part of existing principles or methodologies (OBO, FAIR, and LOT) where they are applicable. Others, like IVOA, do not have overarching principles but develop extensive specifications (standards) within their domain.

In all cases, these initiatives prioritise the quality of their work by adopting good practices and recommendations. Automated or semi-automated tools (e.g., the trait dictionary quality checking tool in the Crop Ontology project or O'FAIRe methodology and tool²⁷ for assessing the level of FAIRness in ontologies) are typically employed in their workflows to validate the quality of the results.

By analysing communities of practice, we have identified key components of the governance framework: **principles, standards, and quality**. We have conceptualised these elements in the following model (Fig. 8) to provide a unified governance structure that will increase interoperability across adopting initiatives.

Figure 8. General governance model of the establishment of principles and recommendations within an organisation.

Principles can be simple statements or concrete policies that cover various aspects of the SA lifecycle (e.g., metadata, versioning, contribution). For example, "*The process of ontology versioning should be encoded by reusing multiple relevant metadata properties from existing vocabularies*" is a fundamental principle (rule) covering the versioning aspect of the SA lifecycle. Each principle should lead to the reuse or creation of specific **Recommendations**

²⁶ <https://saref.etsi.org/principles.html>

²⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMSO.2022.131133>

²⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7007495>

that guide the methodological application of the principle. "*About versioning ontologies or any digital objects with clear semantics*"²⁸ (a research article produced in FAIR-IMPACT T4.2) discusses versioning for SAs by describing methods for encoding versioning and other relevant information in metadata properties. This article provides valuable recommendations regarding the versioning principle we have defined.

Another component is **Standards**, which are established norms or requirements about processes or practices. They should be extracted from recommendations and developed by consensus, serving as definitions to ensure quality, interoperability, and efficiency. For example, in the context of SA versioning, providing a separate Internationalised Resource Identifier (IRI) for identifying each version of an ontology (version IRI) could be an internal standard, along with the semantic versioning specification²⁹ (SemVer), which is a system for version numbers. Web ontology language (OWL) could be another standard for providing properties for establishing the versioning process (e.g. *owl:versionInfo* or *owl:versionIRI*). Establishing these standards enables human or software-based evaluation of their correct implementation through a **Quality control** process. Continuing with the example, an automated test could be defined to query the SA to retrieve the version IRI. If found, this IRI is compared to a regex pattern to determine if it adheres to SemVer. For instance, if an ontology is annotated with the IRI "<https://w3id.org/example/1.0.0>" using the *owl:versionIRI* OWL property, it will successfully pass the test and validate its quality based on versioning standards.

Finally, **Training** should be derived from recommendations. It highlights the need for initiatives to train different stakeholders by explaining the concepts, guidelines, and usage of these recommendations to apply the associated principles effectively.

3. Process followed

Once we analysed the three main components of SA governance and outlined how communities manage them, we developed a methodology to formalise SA governance models. In the first step, we aggregated practices associated with different aspects of the SA lifecycle (e.g., versioning, documentation, metadata, etc.). In the second step, we identified potential target groups for the model. We then developed SA governance models for these groups by integrating practices related to Engineering Methodology and SA lifecycle (Section 2.1 and result of step 1: Table 4), Organisational Structure (Section 2.2), and Governance Framework (Section 2.3). Table 5 presents these models, structured according to the approaches reviewed by the communities under our scrutiny.

Step 1) Our strategy is to examine the principles of each initiative to pinpoint the general aspects of the SA lifecycle that each principle aims to cover. The OBO Foundry principles are our primary source for this step due to their clear documentation and well-established reputation in the academic discipline, making them highly reliable and comprehensive.

²⁸ doi: 10.4126/FRL01-006444994

²⁹ <https://semver.org/>

Their extensive application across various ontologies provide a solid foundation for our analysis.

Principles from BASF serve as a secondary resource, particularly the first principle dedicated to developing and maintaining FAIR ontologies. These principles are valued for their operational approach to ontology governance and their innovative contributions to the field. FAIR ontologies are essential for ensuring that data and information are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, which enhances their utility and integration across diverse systems.

Additionally, we consider other resources such as SAREF design principles, methods from LOT, and ontology governance frameworks to address potential gaps in the primary sources. These supplementary materials help ensure a comprehensive evaluation by incorporating diverse perspectives.

Step 1. a) Align the BASF and OBO principles to identify gaps in each organisation’s policy for managing SAs. These gaps, shown in grey boxes in [Appendix E](#), indicate areas of the SA lifecycle not covered by the principles of one of these initiatives.

Step 1. b) We merged these principles into a single list to address the gaps by combining overlapping principles and retaining the rest from both organisations. We then normalised them to identify the general aspects of the SA lifecycle that each principle aims to cover. The result is shown in Table 3, where each element is tagged with the principle from which it was initially derived.

Table 3. Aspects of SA life cycle result of step 1.b.

Availability (licencing) BASF(P2)-OBO(P1)	Access rights and security policy BASF(P3)-OBO(P1)	Scope OBO(P5)	Documentation BASF(5)-OBO(8)	Mapping BASF(P1)-OBO(P7)	Naming Conventions OBO(P12)
Unique identification for (meta)data BASF(P1)-OBO(P3)	Relevant attributes, metadata and provenance BASF(P1)-OBO(P6,P9)	(Meta)data access and semantic repository BASF(P1)	Persistency (Versioning and Deprecation) BASF(P3)-OBO(P4)	(Meta)data reuse and relevant practices (e.g., Modularity) BASF(P1)-SAREF	Channels for communications and contribution OBO(P13,P16,P20)
	information model BASF(P1)-OBO(P2)	Commitment to collaboration OBO(P10,P11,P16)	SA visualisation LOT Methodology	SA Language LOT Methodology	

Step 1. c) We collected various approaches from the SA governance workshop and related resources to address different aspects of the SA lifecycle (Table 4). Each element may be further divided into several categories to provide more detail.

Table 4. Aggregation of all the practices from the SA governance workshop (Sept. 2023) for different domains within the SA lifecycle.

Implementations observed (workshop)	
<p>Availability (licencing)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> open licence limited licence closed 	<p>Access rights and security policy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> role-based access control (e.g. An SA editor role may have permissions to modify and update the ontology, while a viewer role may only have read-only access.) user attribute-based and resource attribute-based access control

<p style="text-align: center;">Community</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SA is not assigned to a particular community SA receive support from a particular community SA has been derived from a specific community SA is a cross-community/domain 	<p>(access to an SA might be restricted based on user attributes like department or job title.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ad hoc discretionary access control (e.g. a researcher with appropriate permissions on the system who developed an ontology may grant access to specific colleagues or collaborators while restricting access to others.)
<p style="text-align: center;">Persistency (Versioning and Deprecation)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Range: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> not defined policy or commitment versioning and deprecation conventions are defined only for the SA versioning and deprecation conventions are also defined for other documents (e.g., requirements, conceptualisation, tests, etc.). Version and deprecation granularity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SA level SA element (term) level both neither Mechanism for versioning: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> manual versioning (e.g. defining file naming conventions like ontology_v1.0_2024-05-19.owl) automate versioning (e.g. implementation of version control system like git, relying on repositories versioning system) Version numbers convention: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> defining internal convention adopting semantic versioning specification (SemVer) 	<p style="text-align: center;">Documentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Management Plan: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> not stated in the documentation not required optional/recommended for projects in the early stages mandatory Granularity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SA and SA element-level documentation project level documentation Topic: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> requirements documentation design documentation versioning documentation usage documentation development documentation maintenance and support documentation testing documentation compliance and licensing documentation metadata and provenance documentation collaboration and contribution documentation deployment documentation Audience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> human-readable documentation machine-readable documentation
<p style="text-align: center;">Relevant attributes, metadata and provenance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metadata standards: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> no standard has its metadata standards (e.g., OBO Metadata Ontology (OMO)) adopted existing control vocabularies and ontologies Mandatory/recommended and optional metadata (on ontology level and ontology element level) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> not defined defined internally adopted existing rules and recommendations on minimum metadata (e.g., Minimum Information for the Reporting of an Ontology (MIRO)) Type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> structural and descriptive attributes (class, property, hierarchy, instance, annotation property, labels, text descriptions, definitions, synonyms, comments) descriptive metadata (abstract, keywords, references, authors and contribution) administrative metadata (ontology name, title, version information, publisher, project/resource owner, date, licence, documentation, funding information, funding) structural metadata (analysis, methods, sampling procedure and size, categories and variables) provenance (general provenance, creation date, authors and contributors, tools and methodologies, source data, change history, modification date, change reasons, latest changes, usage and application context) access and distribution metadata (publication date, 	<p style="text-align: center;">Unique identification for (meta)data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ontology identifier: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (local) unique identifiers (e.g., UUIDs) global unique and persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI) Ontology elements identifier: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> internal identifier (e.g., stable URIs) external identifier versioned identifier (e.g., version IRI) specific metadata identifier data and metadata share the same identifier (metadata embedded with the data) Management: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> centralised management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> registry authority control system decentralised management (e.g., federated systems) Audience: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> human-readable identifiers (e.g., descriptive strings) machine-readable identifiers (e.g., UUIDs, hash codes) Resolvability: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> unresolvable identifier resolvable identifier <p style="text-align: center;">SA visualisation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diagrams: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> class hierarchies (e.g., tree diagrams) entity-relationship diagrams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> UML Diagrams Graph-based visualisation:

distribution channels like platforms or repositories landing page, access restrictions, downloadable files, API and SPARQL endpoints)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ node-link diagrams ● SPARQL query results visualisation ● tabular visualisation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Tables and spreadsheets
<p style="text-align: center;">information model</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Knowledge representation data model <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Resource Description Framework (RDF) ● Knowledge representation formalism <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Description Logics (DL) ● Knowledge representation language <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ RDF schema (RDFS) ○ Simple Knowledge Organisation System (SKOS) ○ web ontology language (OWL) ○ Unified Medical Language System (UMLS) ○ OBO language ● Formality level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Controlled vocabulary and schema ○ Terminologies ○ Taxonomies ○ Thesaurus ○ Ontology ● Syntax <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only serialised in RDF/XML ○ several serialisations are available (turtle, N-Triples, JSON-LD, N3, etc.) ● Knowledge base (graph) compatible product (appropriate modelling with the vision that the SA will finally use to create knowledge graphs) 	<p style="text-align: center;">(Meta)data access and semantic repository</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Network communication protocols: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ only through HTTP(S) ○ HTTP(S) and SPARQL ● Methods to access the ontology: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ HTTP(S) ○ RDF/OWL Dump files ○ APIs ○ SPARQL endpoint ● Repository type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Internal to project or organisation. ○ external ● Repository domain: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ domain specific (e.g., EcoPortal, BioPortal) ○ Domain generic (e.g., fairsharing.org) ● Repository maturity level: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ indexed ○ no searchable list ○ simple searchable list ○ ontology library/catalogue (e.g., Ontology Lookup Service) ○ SA catalog (e.g., AgroPortal, EcoPortal) ● Repository technology: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ triple store ○ property graph (e.g., Neo4j) ○ relational database
<p style="text-align: center;">(Meta)data reuse</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SA selection: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Strategy: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ SA selection by standardisation (e.g., reuse of ontologies like PROV-O or Time Ontology, which are the W3C standard) ■ SA selection by popularity (reuse of FOAF ontologies) ■ SA selection by performing analysis ○ Implementation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ use of SA repository services (e.g., browse or terms search) ■ use of dedicated tools (e.g., Ontofox) ● Policies for reuse: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ direct reuse <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ soft reuse (referring to external SA elements URIs) ■ hard reuse (import the entire SA) ○ Indirect reuse: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ terms from external SA are reused as a template in the new ontology ○ hybrid reuse ● Ontology integration methods: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Modular composition (allow separation and recombination of different parts of the SA depending on specific needs) 	<p style="text-align: center;">Scope</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SA lacks a statement of the domain or subject matter it intends to cover ● The scope of the SA is defined by the repository where the SA is hosted <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The domain is selected from predefined categories provided by the repository during the SA submission process ● The domain is clearly defined by giving an explicit scope statement <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The documentation clearly outlines the boundaries and content of the SA in a dedicated section of the project's website ● Practices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ focused scope (narrow scope to prevent duplication of terms) ○ handling out-of-scope terms (Import and reuse terms from existing ontologies when required terms fall outside the defined scope) ○ separate modules for out-of-scope terms (Place out-of-scope terms in separate SA that can be imported or exported as needed) ○ extensibility to allow further growth of the SA (different stakeholders specialise the SA concepts according to their needs and points of view, add more specific concepts, relationships and hypotheses to refine the general

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Orthogonality and Merging ● Ontology networking: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Cross-product definitions (reuse terms from other SA in cross-product definitions where appropriate) ○ Conflict Resolution (e.g., addressing overlapping and competing ontologies in the same domain) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (standard) semantics expressed in the reference SA) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ document and respond to community feedback regarding the scope and content of the SA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ ensure that generic terms meet the needs of the broader community
<p style="text-align: center;">Naming Conventions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● no establishment of naming conventions ● align naming conventions with existing standards and guidelines (e.g., OBO naming convention) where applicable ● establishment of concrete naming conventions ● Type: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ domain-specific ○ generic or cross-domain (extendible) ● Target format: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ OBO ○ OWL 	<p style="text-align: center;">Channels for communications and contribution</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● None ● Direct communication: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ personal email ○ project-specific email ○ Messaging platforms: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ instant messaging (e.g., slack, Microsoft Teams) ■ group chats ● Public discussion forums: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ project/community mailing list ○ announcement mailing list (for pre-announcing changes and updates) ○ online forums <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ project-specific forum ■ public SA related forum (e.g., BioPortal Forum) ● Collaborating platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Version control repositories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ GitHub/GitLab issues ■ pull requests and code reviews ■ GitHub pre-releases ○ project/community wiki pages ● Community contribution: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ feedback forms ○ community surveys ● Specialised communication channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ dedicated support channels (e.g., helpdesk) ○ Advisory panels (reflect changes in scientific consensus to keep the SA accurate over time): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ scientific advisory boards ■ user advisory panels
<p style="text-align: center;">Commitment to collaboration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community engagement <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ open forums and discussion boards ○ workshops and meetings ○ contribution guidelines (transparent contribution processes and agreements) ○ training and mentorship programs ● Tools for supporting collaborative ontology development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ online document editors (e.g., Google Docs) ○ collaborative editing platforms (e.g., web protege) ○ issue tracker ● Contact authority: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ primary contact person <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ optional ■ mandatory ○ alternative contacts ○ to date, contact information <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ included in metadata embedded with the SA file) ■ submitted in the registry (which will be available in a separate metadata file) 	

Step 2) In practice, SA governance is inherently situational, reflecting each organisation's unique characteristics and needs. The approach to management is influenced by several factors, including organisational goals and structure, technological capabilities and infrastructure, regulatory and compliance requirements, data complexity and volume, stakeholders' involvement, and cultural factors. However, despite these differences, it is essential to establish consistent, interoperable principles that can harmonise SA governance across various domains. Such principles provide a common framework that facilitates alignment and integration, ensuring that governance practices can effectively support cross-domain interoperability while accommodating diverse organisational contexts.

To develop effective models that accommodate a wide variety of initiatives and communities, we compared several factors mentioned in the previous paragraph across nine communities from the SA governance workshop. This comparative analysis led us to identify distinct models, each representing a set of common features and governance practices observed across these communities. These models provide recommendations in which

different components of SA governance and management can be applied in a manner that reflects the unique characteristics and needs of each initiative. As a result, we defined the following general models that capture these shared characteristics:

- **1) SA Project-based initiatives** managing individual SAs, such as application ontologies (e.g., **EFO** and **SAREF**) or Linked Open Data sets (e.g., **AGROVOC**). Within this category, SA is developed to address the need for standard vocabulary in a target domain. These SA enable semantic interoperability and support the creation of knowledge graphs by providing domain-specific concepts and properties, enhancing data integration between systems that deploy them.
- **2) Distributed SA development and support-based initiatives** support communities in developing and maintaining (FAIR and open) SAs. Individuals or groups of researchers independently build and maintain artefacts in a decentralised manner. Organisations such as **INRAE Voc** and **NFDI4Biodiv** operate within this category.
- **3) SA Harmonisation initiatives** that provide principles and guidelines, along with infrastructure, to harmonise the management of SA across communities or organisations. Developers can use the upper-level ontologies, modularisation methods, and other standard workflows and practices established by these initiatives to ensure they develop interoperable SA. **The OBO Foundry** is an example of this category, serving as a pivotal point in using semantic web technologies in biological and biomedical sciences. **BASF** also falls into this category but restricts its developed ontologies to internal organisational use.

4. Semantic artefact governance models

The governance of SA extends beyond decision making. While the interaction between actors and their accountability for different domains of the SA life cycle is crucial, it must be guided by well-defined rules aligned with the organisation's or community's goals. A holistic view is essential, encompassing all requirements for SA management, from the maturity level of infrastructure and processes to the capabilities of human resources. This comprehensive approach ensures all elements work cohesively to achieve the desired outcomes.

Organisations and communities adopt varied methods and processes for the development and management of SA, tailored to their structures and capacities. As long as these approaches meet their objectives, they prove effective. Therefore, a range of strategies can address diverse organisational needs. Following the structured methodology, we analysed practices, principles, and resources for SA governance to create tailored models that cater to the specific requirements of distinct target groups. In this section, we present these models in detail, highlighting the practical outcomes of our approach and providing a framework for effective SA governance.

Table 5. FAIR-IMPACT proposed Semantic Artefact Governance and Management models.

SA Governance components		Model #1: SA project-based Initiatives	Model #2: Distributed SA development and support-based Initiatives	Model #3: SA harmonisation Initiatives
Governance Framework	Principles	Where applicable, follow existing principles (e.g., OBO, FAIR, LOT, 5 Star Data ³⁰).	Inform the community about existing principles and provide guidelines for establishing them.	Define clear principles and provide infrastructure to support the community or organisation toward its goals and objectives for managing SA.
	Recommendations	Consider good practice and recommendations.	Guide the community to existing practices and recommendations.	Create comprehensive recommendations, implementation guidelines and examples for different aspects of the SA life cycle.
	Standards	Adopt W3C standards and guidelines to ensure a high level of quality.	Set the baseline standards across communities to facilitate the quality evaluation of SA.	Adhere to W3C standards and guidelines, contribute to them and define new ones as needed.
	Quality control	Adopt software engineering practices (e.g., implementing version control systems) and use ontology validators and evaluators.	Guide the community in using software engineering practices and quality evaluator tools throughout the different stages of the SA lifecycle. Develop pipelines and tests tailored to the specific needs of the community.	Integrate the infrastructure with quality evaluator tools. Develop (openly) available quality control processes, tests, and tools for validating the implementation of principles and standards defined across the community or organisation.
	Training	Relying on training materials available, maybe set up training sessions for primary users (e.g., systems that implemented the SA).	Organise training sessions for the community to educate them about the principles and recommendations followed and how to ensure the quality of SA.	Hold workshops to elaborate on each principle and recommendation within the community or organisation. Engage in long-term training and support activities.
Aspects of SA lifecycle	Availability (licencing)	Make an SA available with clear licensing terms.	Inform the community about the benefits of choosing an open licence to maintain their copyright while enabling the public to reuse their SA.	Develop guidelines and workflows to support the licensing process. Associate the licensing to a principle.
	Access rights and security policy	Manage the permissions granted to different individuals within the SA lifecycle.	Provide guidelines on methods and tools for implementing a secure access policy.	Establish an access rights management system. Create a document that outlines policies and strategies for an organisation to maintain the security of its SA.
	Versioning	Identify each version of the SA using a unique IRI.	Guide the community towards relevant practices and encourage them to establish a plan (workflows) for the	Provide a formal versioning process to track different iterations of the SA (and associated documentation), ensuring transparency and

³⁰ <https://5stardata.info/en/>

		periodic release of new versions of SA.	effective change management. Provide infrastructure and tools to support these aspects.
Deprecation	Establish a deprecation process at the SA element (term) level and notify primary users of updated or alternative terms upon deprecation.	Guide the community towards relevant practices for deprecation.	Establish a deprecation process at the SA and SA element (term) levels. Provide formal mechanisms to encode and support these aspects.
Documentation	Create a human-readable description of the SA (HTML pages) to enhance understanding of its structure and content. Where relevant, provide documentation on critical aspects of the SA lifecycle (e.g., versioning, testing, data access, etc.).	Motivate the community to provide documentation for their SA development and curation processes and potential SA usage. Encourage the use of selected semantic artefact catalogues (SACs).	Provide documentation on the potential use of infrastructure services. Develop or integrate services into the infrastructure to automate the generation of HTML pages based on SA structure and content. Work along with selected SACs.
Unique identification for (meta)data	Assign a globally unique and persistent identifier to the SA(maybe SA metadata, and SA elements). Resolve each of them to their respective representations as requested by the client, using redirection practice and content negotiation mechanisms.	Define the namespace naming conventions. Inform the community about redirection, resolution, and PID provider services. To support this, maybe associate them with selected SACs.	Develop the policy for creating harmonised and interoperable namespaces within the community or organisation. Integrate redirection and PID provider services into the ontology development workflows and systems to automate the assignment of identifiers to SA, SA metadata, and SA elements and facilitate the management of related representations. Work with selected SACs to reflect these aspects.
Relevant attributes, metadata and provenance	Use common metadata standards to provide rich context to ontology and ontology terms in different aspects such as description, administration, and provenance.	Establish minimum standards metadata for reporting SA within the community. Encourage the use of selected SACs dealing with metadata and provenance.	Establish internal metadata schemas alongside existing metadata standards to provide customised classes and properties for reporting SA. Implement these schemas and standards within SACs.
(Meta)data access and semantic repository	Host the SA (metadata) on web (application) servers or tools, such as an ad hoc SKOSMOS installation, a triple store (e.g., Virtuoso), or SA catalogues, to make it accessible via HTTP(S).	Introduce the community to domain-specific SA catalogues where they can publish their SA, making them findable and accessible through services for term lookup, ontology explorations and dedicated APIs.	Develop SACs or components, such as web applications, repositories, dedicated APIs, SPARQL endpoints, and related services, to facilitate SA (metadata) management and access.
Information model	Utilise RDF(s), OWL, SKOS, and other W3C standards as core vocabularies for encoding and structuring SA. Offer one or more serialisations of the SA in acceptable syntax formats.	Advocate for using W3C standards when selecting knowledge representation languages for SA development within the community. Recommend using specific representation languages and syntax to ease interoperability.	Enforce certain (W3C) standards for knowledge representation languages in SA development within an organisation. Develop standard pipelines for transformation between different SA formality levels. Additionally, it provides services to produce SA source files and convert them between various SA serialisations.

(Meta)data reuse	Identify and reuse specific terms or patterns defined in existing SA rather than creating new ones from scratch.	Provide a primary list of selected SA for reuse or direct the community to tools that help locate their desired SA for reuse. (e.g., ontofox ³¹).	Enforce some practices, including specific properties, in terms of reuse to help create interoperable SA networks within an organisation. Reuse upper-level ontologies to support broad semantic interoperability. Provide methodologies for modular development and pattern reuse.
Visualisation	Provide visual representations for the SA.	Direct the community to tools for visualising SA.	Provide visualisation services in the systems to provide hierarchical, graphical, and tabular representations of the SA.
Mapping	Link the SA terms to equivalent terms in other relevant SAs by using standard properties such as skos:closeMatches, rdfs:seeAlso, owl:sameAlso, owl:equivalentClass, dcterms:relation, etc.	Encourage the community to contribute mappings to other relevant SA terms.	Establish a framework to harmonise and manage the mapping process within the initiative. Create a dedicated SA to provide properties for use in mappings.
Naming Conventions	Choose standard label properties (RDFS, SKOS) to provide a primary label or synonym for every SA term.	Encourage the community to follow established naming conventions based on W3C standards.	Provide detailed documents for establishing naming conventions within the organisation. Contribute and complete naming convention standards when necessary for a harmonised use.
Scope	Prepare a brief text document that clearly states the extent of the domain the SA intends to cover.	Ensure that SA developed within the community has a well-defined scope and content consistent with that scope.	Urge the organisation to clearly state what is out of scope while also identifying and linking to the specific users and use cases the SA aims to address.
Commitment to collaboration	Utilise tools that facilitate collaborative SA development, such as collaborative editing platforms. Illustrate the usage of SA outside of the immediate circle of stakeholders.	Ensure all SA is assigned a contact person (with detailed information) to facilitate communication between the community and the SA providers. Define a dedicated role responsible for communications between the community and the SA providers.	Organise collaborative workshops to ensure the orthogonality of distinct SAs. Address topics such as reusing content from other artefacts, determining domain divisions between ontologies, evaluating the potential merger of ontologies into a single artefact, etc. Set up and enforce required collaboration practices and tools.
Channels for communications and contribution	Create responsive channels to collect feedback and term requests from users and domain experts and keep them informed about updates to the SA.	Host public forums to promote knowledge sharing among various stakeholders in the community or suggest practices (e.g. forums on SACs or issue trackers) to ease feedback and communications.	Establish scientific and user advisory boards within the organisation. Develop curation and maintenance workflows (e.g., term requests and issue resolution) and integrate them into the SA lifecycle.

³¹ ontofox.hegroup.org

Organisational structure	Coordination level	Appoint a Project Manager responsible for overseeing the design, conduct, and reporting of the SA project. The Project Manager will manage and monitor collaborative relationships, fulfilling all technical, scientific, financial, and administrative obligations necessary to maintain project standards and ensure process integrity. Additionally, the Project Manager will investigate widely used principles and best practices, adopting those most suitable for the project.	Assign a Coordination role to an individual or team responsible for defining the strategy to support the community in managing SAs. This includes providing targeted principles, recommendations, guidelines, relevant tools, services, training materials, consulting programs, and workshops. The Coordinator will outline responsibilities and accountabilities for stakeholders within the community—ranging from SA owners and curators to experts and contributors—and coordinate activities across the website, repository, and communication channels.	Appoint a Coordinator or a team to manage the SA infrastructure, focusing on website, repository, relevant services, quality assurance processes, regular updates to guidelines, and an effective governance framework. The Coordinator will consult with curators to gather feedback and assess needs, oversee principles, documentation and guidelines to ensure consistency with governance standards, and monitor the impact of the SAs. Additionally, the Coordinator will lead outreach activities with the Community, engage community members in decision-making and communication, mediate conflicts, and address strategic organisational issues.
	Initiative level	Define a technical role or team responsible for developing and maintaining the project website or catalogue where the SA is published, and for supporting related services, such as APIs. Additionally, establish a role for communicating with users of the SA. If the SA is only accessible online through an external catalogue, a curator may be sufficient to report potential issues with this external catalogue and related services, and to communicate with users of the SA.	Create dedicated documentation outlining the principles and standards that the community is encouraged to follow. Establish a website or helpdesk to guide various stakeholders and provide support for implementing good practices and shared tools within the community. Include technical activities for developing and maintaining this website or helpdesk.	Establish an Editorial Committee to develop and maintain the organisation’s principles, create a review process for them, conduct reviews, and set policies governing these processes. Form a Technical Team responsible for maintaining the technical infrastructure, including the website, repositories, APIs, SPARQL endpoints, and related services and workflows. Establish an Outreach Group to manage public relations for the organisation by monitoring and following up on communication channels, preparing documentation and educational materials, and representing the organisation at venues.
	Semantic artefact level	Alongside ontology developers and contributors, define an ontology curator who will: - Regularly review the ontology to integrate new data and adapt it to evolving requirements. - Oversee key aspects of the SA lifecycle, including versioning, deprecation, mapping, identification, and the publication. - Maintain a broad network of contacts within the community, expert groups, coordination teams, and relevant external parties to ensure ongoing collaboration and knowledge sharing.	Make sure each SA is assigned to a curator and define a baseline set of responsibilities for them. Establish a working group within the community to assess the need for new SAs and provide feedback on existing ones and their potential applications. Facilitate connections between diverse stakeholders and relevant existing scientific domain experts in the community.	Establish a curator committee to serve as a standing body that facilitates communication among all curators. Form an expert group to support curators in SA validation and curation within specific areas of expertise, promote the use of SAs across the organisation, provide guidance for the evolution of SA content and the reuse of other SAs, and validate corresponding modifications.

5. Conclusions

The exploration of SA governance within the EOSC context (and beyond) highlights its multifaceted and critical role in digital data management and interoperability. As the EOSC strives to establish a unified, open environment for data and services, the governance of SAs becomes indispensable for seamless integration and interoperability across varied scientific domains.

Our analysis has underscored the complexity of SA governance, revealed through the diversity of methodologies and practices across different scientific communities. This diversity points to a lack of a universally accepted definition of SA governance; however, it broadly aligns with the principles and frameworks that standardise and manage the lifecycle of SAs. These include their creation, development, utilisation, and eventual disposal, incorporating decision-making structures, stakeholder roles, and operational mechanisms to maintain the integrity, interoperability, and longevity of SAs.

We identified three foundational pillars of SA governance: *Engineering Methodologies*, *Organisational Structure*, and *Governance Frameworks*, each contributing uniquely to the landscape. Each pillar shapes how SA is managed and governed within different communities and organisations. These pillars facilitate systematic approaches to SA development and management, define roles and responsibilities within the processes, and set overarching rules and standards that enhance adherence to FAIR principles and ensure data quality and metadata management.

SA governance model implementation varies significantly across initiatives, reflecting scientific communities' diverse needs, contexts, and objectives. While some adopt centralised governance structures with formalised decision-making bodies, others favour decentralised, flexible, community-driven approaches. This diversity highlights the adaptable nature of SA governance and underscores the necessity for models that can evolve with changing technologies, scientific practices, and community dynamics.

Moving forward, the development of reusable SA governance and management models presents both challenges and opportunities. It requires a profound synthesis of practices and principles from successful initiatives like the OBO Foundry, Crop Ontology project, GOMO-BASF, and others. **Our proposed models:**

- **Model #1: Project-based Initiatives** (i.e., initiatives managing individual SA),
- **Model #2: Distributed SA Development and support based initiatives** (i.e., initiatives supporting decentralised SA development efforts),
- **Model #3: SA Harmonisation Initiatives** (i.e., initiatives harmonising SA management practices across a community or a company),

are tailored to meet the distinct needs of several target groups. They are designed to enhance data sharing, collaboration, and innovation within scientific communities, thereby advancing the objectives and vision of the EOSC.

The journey towards effective SA governance and management in the context of EOSC is ongoing. Stakeholders are encouraged to continue refining and harmonising practices, leveraging lessons learned from a broad spectrum of initiatives to foster innovation, accelerate research outcomes, and ensure the sustainable impact of SAs in advancing scientific knowledge and discovery. This collaborative approach will enhance the interoperability and reusability of SAs and pave the way for more efficient and transparent data management practices in support of FAIR principles. By addressing challenges and embracing collaborative governance models, stakeholders can foster innovation, accelerate research outcomes, and ensure the long-term sustainability and impact of SAs in advancing scientific knowledge and discovery, thereby significantly contributing to the objectives and vision of the EOSC.

6. Appendices

Appendix A. List of CROP, OBO Foundry and BASF stakeholders' structuration and description of their roles and responsibilities

Community	CROP	OBO Foundry	BASF
Categories			
Findability	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sources	-Governance document ³² -Actors Roles webpage ³³ -Actors members webpage ³⁴	- Webpage ³⁵	-Governance document ³⁶
Formal groups	Yes	Yes	No
Name of the groups (Stakeholders)	-Committees: -Curators Committee -Strategy Committee -Scientific Advisory Committee -Team: -CO team (Technical and Ontology coordinators)	-Committees: -Operations Committee (Editorial, Technical and Outreach working groups) -Code of Conduct Committee -Working groups (WG): -Editorial WG -Technical WG -Outreach WG	-Team -Data semantic team
Description of stakeholders' roles and responsibilities	Yes	Yes	No
Raw description (Stakeholders group Responsibilities)	CO management institute -Accept responsibility to manage the overall CO project -Appoint the Ontology Coordinator and Technical Coordinator	Operations committee: Members of the OBO Foundry Operations Committee aim to	-ontology developer -ontology owner -ontology curator

³² CROP Ontology "Governance and Stewardship Framework" document:

<https://cgspace.cgiar.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/548034d0-445b-4de3-9050-708941f0a790/content>

³³ CROP Ontology stakeholder's roles webpage : <https://cropontology.org/page/Advisoryroles>

³⁴ CROP Ontology stakeholder's members webpage : <https://cropontology.org/page/MembersAC>

³⁵ OBO Foundry stakeholder's organisation webpage : <http://obofoundry.org/about-OBO-Foundry.html>

³⁶ BASF "Governance operational model of ontologies" document : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7007495>

<p>Individual)</p>	<p>-Provide necessary resources to maintain the website and develop necessary new features</p> <p>CO team: Technical and Ontology Coordinators</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ontology coordinator -Lead the CO team at the global level on behalf of the CO Management Institute -Manage the product, its content, its website and the quality assurance process -Manage the regular update of the Guidelines and Template, quality checking tools, validation and that curation roles are in place. -Maintain a practical governance framework - Regularly consult the community of curators to get feedback and needs -Interact with the Strategy Committee to get timely recommendations on global CO strategy -Validation of new crops after checking if the governing roles are in place -Allocate unique crop codes from the CO list -Guide users -Initiate fundraising and engage resources -Lead the outreach activities with the Ontologies Community of Practice -Engage community members in decision making and communication <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Technical coordinator -Member of the CO team -Update the CO content by providing guidance and expertise to curators -Promote the use of best practices concerning Crop Ontology development - Contribute to the discussion around content and CO domain boundaries -Guide the use of other ontologies functional in agriculture -Contribute to the improvement and maintenance of the Template and Guidelines -Maintain & upgrade, in collaboration with the developer, the CO website backend & frontend according to users' requirements -Maintain the domain name of the CO website -Check crop ontologies for quality and inconsistencies -Operate ontology helpdesk -Promotion of the CO -Create the term mappings with Planteome -Technical interactions with ontology registries and the breeding databases -Training of curators 	<p>improve the flow of operations and make things happen within the OBO Foundry. Such operations include, but are not limited to, establishment of policies, review of resources, outreach and education.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Editorial WG is responsible for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Principles: drafting text and creating the workflow and guidelines for the principles development process -Ontologies: reviewing and creating the workflow and guidelines for the ontology review process -Policies: crafting the policies for the above -Technical WG is involved in maintaining the technical infrastructure for the OBO Foundry. This includes establishing policies to be implemented in standard tools, website maintenance, etc. -Outreach WG is involved in public relations for the OBO Foundry. This includes monitoring and following up discussions on mailing lists, preparing documentation and educational materials, and presenting OBO Foundry activities at workshops, conferences, or other venues. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -domain expert -end-user
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	<p><i>Curators committee</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Group of Curators representing all crop ontology curators -Selected by the members of the curator community for a term of up to 2 years -Acts as a standing body to facilitate communication between the entire curator community and the CO Team <p>Strategy Committee</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Committee with representatives from crop domains, CO global project domain and external domain (including representatives of Breeding databases and ontology registries) -Provide recommendations to the CO Ontology Coordinator on strategic project issues <p>Scientific Advisory Committee</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Committee with representatives from crop domains and external (scientific) domain -Provide advice to the CO Team on scientific issues relevant to the CO -Provide guidance and recommendations for the evolution of the Crop Ontology content and technology, identification of best practices regarding the use of CO or other ontologies -Provide expertise and guidance for the homogenisation of entities and attribute terms across species – e.g. a tissue name -Validate the quality assurance tools proposed by the Community that can be promoted through CO -Validate for some species a group of experts who could evaluate the submissions (homogeneity). The group would make critical assessments (redundancy checking, homogenisation of terms, etc.). -Validate the modifications of the Trait Dictionary Template and accompanying Guidelines in consultation with the Ontology and Technical Coordinators 	<p>Code of Conduct committee is responsible for ensuring the OBO Code of Conduct is upheld.</p>	
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Appendix B. List of INRAE Voc, IVOA and NFDI4Biodiv stakeholders' structuration and description of their roles and responsibilities

Community	INRAE Voc	IVOA	NFDI4Biodiv
Categories			
Findability			
Sources	No	Yes	No
Formal groups (Stakeholders)	-	-Actors webpage ³⁷ - IVOA wikipage ³⁸ - Decision process document ³⁹	
Formal groups (Stakeholders)	Yes	Yes	Yes
Name of the groups (Stakeholders)	-Committees: -Editorial Committee	-Committees: -Executive Committee -Standing Committee on Science Priorities (CSP) -Standing Committee on Standards & Processes (SCSP) -IUA-IVOA Liaison Committee (IILG) Groups: -Technical Coordination Group (TCG) (WG chair and vice-chair; IG chair and vice-chair; -TCG chair and vice-chair; -IVOA chair and vice-chair; Chair of SCSP) -Working groups (WGs) (Applications, Data Access Layer, Data Model, Grid and Web Services, Registry and Semantics) -Interest group (IGs) (Data Curation & Preservation, Education, Knowledge Discovery in Databases, Operations, Solar System, Theory, Time Domain, Radio, High Energy) -Media Group	-Committees: -Taxonomies Editorial Committee -Board: -Taxonomies Editorial Board -Groups: -Tasks groups
Description of stakeholders' roles and responsibilities	Yes	Yes	Yes
Raw description (Stakeholders group)	Editorial Committee Provide editorial guidelines in SA	Executive committee Review and approve WG recommendations	Taxonomies Editorial Committees <i>oversee taxonomy-related</i>

³⁷ IVOA stakeholder's members webpage : <https://www.ivoa.net/members/>

³⁸ IVOA wikipage : <https://wiki.ivoa.net/twiki/bin/view/IVOA/WebHome>

³⁹ IVOA "Document Standards" : <https://www.ivoa.net/documents/DocStd/20170517/>

<p>Responsibilities Individual)</p>	<p>quality and maintenance</p> <p>SA authors Decision of SA development and maintenance</p> <p>External experts Ensure scientific quality</p>	<p>CSP <i>The primary goal of the CSP is to support the Executive Committee in its goal of sustaining the VO's impact, as follows:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Advise the Executive Committee on strategies for engaging the astronomical community as a participant in the Virtual Observatory. -<i>Demonstrate to the community the benefits of participation in the IVOA, such as the growth in the scientific return of data, the capability to discover and fuse multiple data sets, and the application of the VO in planning new observations and observing strategies.</i> -Recommend scientific priorities and requirements that will drive the development of new services, protocols, and tools. The IVOA will develop these and coordinate with the TCG. These priorities should be driven by scientific use cases developed in cooperation with the scientific community. -Support the TCG in the development of protocols to ensure they meet the actual scientific requirements -Support VO members in developing tutorials, workshops and scientific training materials. <p>SCSP <i>The Standing Committee on Standards and Processes (SCSP) reviews and updates IVOA processes in response to the needs of the IVOA community. When such updates necessitate the revision of an IVOA standard, the same processes apply to the review and promotion of that standard as when the revisions originate with a Working Group, with the chair of the Committee playing the same role as the chair of a Working Group.</i></p> <p>IILG <i>role is to support the IAU's goals in astronomy and promote the value of the Virtual Observatory, especially its value in promoting Open Science and FAIR principles, to the IAU's international community</i></p> <p>TCG <i>-is to ensure proper technical coordination amongst the various IVOA WGs and IGs and a liaison role between them and the IVOA Executive Committee.</i> <i>-the vocabulary is updated, and the IVOA Technical Coordination Group (TCG) endorses this update, potentially prompting additional discussions at the IVOA</i></p>	<p><i>decisions and quality control.</i></p> <p>Taxonomies Editorial Board <i>ensure the quality and accuracy of taxonomic information by making informed decisions about taxonomy updates and changes.</i></p> <p>Task groups - <i>work collaboratively to establish consensus on data and metadata standards.</i> - <i>drive decisions on standards and best practices for biodiversity data through consensus-building processes</i></p> <p>Ontology Manager <i>responsible for ontology structure, content, and versioning decisions.</i></p> <p>Experts in biodiversity domains <i>contribute domain-specific expertise and validate artefacts.</i></p>
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		<p>level.</p> <p>WG <i>Produces specifications, guidelines etc..[...] that may process to recommendation</i></p> <p>IG Share best practices and engage IVOA members' projects in the topic.</p> <p>Media Group <i>aims to disseminate the latest news and information about Virtual Observatory developments, applications, standards, workshops, meetings, etc., to astronomers via various channels, including social media. Messages will be catered to IVOA members and primarily to the general astronomy community to show the benefits of the VO for their science. To achieve this, the Media Group's central areas are Social Media, the IVOA Newsletter, the IVOA Web page and Outreach.</i></p>	
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Appendix C. List of EMBL-EBI, SAREF and AGROVOC stakeholders' structuration and description of their roles and responsibilities

Community	EMBL-EBI	SAREF	AGROVOC
Categories			
Findability	EMBL-EBI	SAREF	AGROVOC
Sources	Not Found	Yes	Yes
Formal groups (Stakeholders)	-Actors webpage ⁴⁰ -Team webpage ⁴¹	- Pipeline document ⁴² - Technical Specification document ⁴³ -Specialist Task Force (STF): 641 webpage ⁴⁴ and STF 653 webpage ⁴⁵	- Webpage ⁴⁶ -Editorial guidelines document ⁴⁷ -Semantic data interoperability document ⁴⁸
Formal groups (Stakeholders)	Yes	Yes	Yes
Name of the groups (Stakeholders)	-Team -Samples, phenotypes and ontology (SPOT) team -Ontology Application team -Semantic data integration service team		-Team: -AGROVOC team -Board -Core Board
Description of stakeholders' roles and responsibilities	Not Found	Yes	Yes
Raw description (Stakeholders group)	SPOT team: <i>Actively develops ontologies,</i>	Steering actors: -Steering Board members	Core board

⁴⁰ EMBL-EBI stakeholder's members webpage : <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/about/teams/samples-phenotypes-ontologies/members/>

⁴¹ EMBL-EBI team organisation webpage: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/about/teams/samples-phenotypes-ontologies/about/>

⁴² " SAREF Pipeline and Portal-An Ontology Verification Framework" document: <https://hal-emse.ccsd.cnrs.fr/emse-04277942v1/document>

⁴³ SAREF "Development Framework and Workflow, Streamlining the Development of SAREF and its Extensions" document:

https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/103600_103699/103673/01.01.01_60/ts_103673v010101p.pdf

⁴⁴ SAREF STF 641 SAREF Digital Twins webpage: <https://portal.etsi.org/xdfs/#/xTF/641/what-we-do>

⁴⁵ SAREF STF 653 SAREF Patterns webpage: <https://portal.etsi.org/xdfs/#/xTF/653/how-we-do>

⁴⁶ AGROVOC webpage : <https://www.fao.org/agrovoc/about>

⁴⁷ AGROVOC "Editorial Guidelines" document : <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb8640en>

⁴⁸ AGROVOC "Semantic data interoperability on food and agriculture" document : <https://doi.org/10.4060/cb2838en>

<p>Responsibilities Individual)</p>	<p><i>including the Cell Type Ontology and Experimental Factor Ontology.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Semantic data integration -Ontology application team -Semantic data integration service team <p><i>deliver Lookup Service</i></p> <p>External collaborations <i>Projects range in scope from data analysis and generation projects to projects delivering infrastructure.</i></p> <p>Project leader:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Technical project leader -Project lead -Ontology project lead <p>Manager:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Scientific programme manager -Research management office lead <p>Coordinator:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Catalogue coordinator - Ontology project coordinator <p>Editors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ontology editorial lead - Ontology editor <p>Developers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Software Developer -Software engineer -Software developer-ontology tools - Ontology developer -Semantic web developer 	<p><i>belongs to the persons in charge of steering the SAREF development, including SAREF core and SAREF extensions. The community involvement and the underlying infrastructure. [...] then review these change requests.</i></p> <p><i>-is it composed of the SmartM2M Chairman, Vice-Chairman, Technical Officer, and experts nominated by SmartM2M?</i> (Workflow 1: new SAREF project version and Workflow 3: project release)</p> <p>-Technical Board members <i>belong to the persons in charge of maintaining the SAREF public forge and the SAREF public portal.</i></p> <p><i>- is composed of ETSI Secretariat and experts nominated by SmartM2M.</i> (Workflow 1: new SAREF project version, Workflow 2: project version development, Workflow 3: project release)</p> <p>Development actors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Project leader <p><i>is the person in charge of the SAREF project who carries out the project management tasks.[...] may have at least the role of Maintainer in the ETSI public forge.</i></p> <p><i>The project leader ensures that SmartM2M approves the change requests and that the implementations satisfy the requested change.</i> (Workflow 1: new SAREF project version, Workflow 2: project version development, Workflow 3: project release)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ontology developer <p><i>is a member of the ontology development team who has high knowledge about ontology development and rights to modify the ontology and interact in the development cycle [...] create and modify the different development artefacts, provide new requirements to the ontology and validate whether they are satisfied or not when implemented, and have decision rights about what contributions can be included in the ontology [...] also review change requests, propose, and review</i></p>	<p><i>-comprises the FAO and KTBL team, and decision-making follows established guidelines, seeking consensus through annual meetings of the AGROVOC Editorial community.</i></p> <p><i>-maintains consistency and coherence per AGROVOC Editorial Guidelines, continually improving curation workflows.</i></p> <p>Coordination and technical support (FAO) Development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -key stakeholders include FAO, The Kuratorium für Technik und Bauwesen in der Landwirtschaft (KTBL), and Tor Vergata University (Italy) -FAO and Tor Vergata University (Italy): the management of specialised concept schemes is possible within AGROVOC <p>Maintenance: (FAO) <i>FAO keeps AGROVOC current, with several institutions and individual domain experts as focal points for specific languages or topics.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -FAO carries mainly the responsibility for the six FAO languages (English, French, Spanish, Arabic, Chinese and Russian), -facilitates the technical maintenance of AGROVOC, including its publication as a Linked Open Data resource, and coordinates all editorial activities <p>Update: (editors & AGROVOC team) <i>Our editors and our team update it continuously. Updated AGROVOC content is released once a month.</i></p> <p>Editors <i>maintained by a vast community of experts and institutions,</i></p>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Web developer <p>Curators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Scientific curator -Senior curator -Catalogue curator <p>-Bioinformatic developer</p> <p>-Bioinformatician</p> <p>Data Engineer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Data Engineer -Semantic data engineer 	<p><i>implementations of accepted change requests.</i> <i>(Workflow 2: project version development-</i></p> <p>Experts <i>may be nominated by SmartM2M to become a development actor for some SAREF projects.</i></p> <p>Community actors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Contributor <p><i>is knowledgeable about the ontology domain and proposes contributions [...] have an account on the SAREF public forge. The role of the contributor is not assigned beforehand; it is obtained when submitting some contribution.</i> <i>(Workflow 1: new SAREF project version, Workflow 2: project version development, Workflow 3: project release)</i></p> <p>-Ontology user <i>may start contributing to some SAREF projects and become a Contributor [...] if interested in any of the SAREF projects or in proposing a new project [...] do not have an account on the SAREF public forge [...] include potential end users of the ontology. These software developers, industry stakeholders, researchers, domain experts, etc., will use the ontology within their applications.</i></p> <p>The SAREF public forge <i>allows users to be defined in the following roles: Guest, Reporter, Developer, Maintainer, and Owner, each with its permissions.</i></p> <p>European Commission and the ETSI SmartM2M Technical Committee.</p> <p><i>Overseen SAREF governance</i></p>	<p>AGROVOC is edited using Vocbench and validated by the AGROVOC team Editor Community AGROVOC Dgroup</p> <p>Curators(FAO and expert external) <i>-expert communities can now curate a topic within AGROVOC, enriching AGROVOC with specialist knowledge, with modern infrastructure to share this as part of the AGROVOC Linked Open data</i> <i>-curatorial responsibilities involve FAO and a team of 40 experts from 34 organisations across 24 countries.</i></p> <p>Social media <i>-[AGROVOC team] organises periodical in-person and virtual meetings with the editorial community and community of experts to maintain and coordinate all contributions to AGROVOC.</i> <i>-endeavours to publish and document the work done in the context of standards, technology and good practices in the agricultural domain.</i></p> <p>AGROVOC team (FAO)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -manager -Curator -Technical lead -Technical support -Communication support <p>External experts <i>-40 experts from 34 organisations across 24 countries.</i></p>
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Appendix D. Distribution of stakeholder names assigned by each surveyed community according to their domain of activity. Italics represent the name of the stakeholder group or individual assigned by each community, and * identify stakeholders who do not have descriptions of their accountabilities.

Domain of activity Communities surveyed	Editorial	Expertise	Outreach	Coordination	Technical	Project management	SA curation	SA development
CROP	<i>Strategy committee; Scientific committee</i>	<i>Scientific Committee</i>	<i>Ontology coordinator</i>	<i>CO team (Technical and ontology coordinator)</i>	<i>Technical coordinator</i>	<i>CO team; CO management institute</i>	<i>Curator committee; Ontology coordinator</i>	<i>CO team</i>
OBO Foundry	<i>Editorial Committee</i>	-	<i>Outreach WG</i>	<i>Technical WG; Editorial WG</i>	<i>Technical WG</i>	-	<i>Technical WG</i>	<i>Technical WG</i>
BASF	-	<i>Domain experts*</i>	-	-	<i>Developers*</i>	<i>Ontology owner*</i>	<i>Ontology curators*</i>	<i>Developers*</i>
INRAE Voc	<i>Editorial Committee</i>	<i>External experts</i>	-	-	-	<i>SA authors*</i>	<i>Editorial committee; experts</i>	<i>Editorial Committee</i>
IVOA	<i>WGs; Executive committee, IGs</i>	<i>CSP committee</i>	<i>CSP committee; Media Group</i>	<i>Executive committee; TCG; SCSP committee</i>	-	-	-	<i>TCG</i>
NFDI4Biodiv	<i>Tasks groups: Taxonomies editorial board</i>	<i>Task groups; Experts</i>	-	<i>Taxonomies editorial committees</i>	-	-	<i>Experts</i>	<i>Ontology manager</i>
EMBL-EBI	<i>Ontology editorial lead*</i>	<i>Scientific curator*; scientific programme manager*</i>	-	<i>Coordinators* (Catalogue*; ontology project coordinator)*</i>	<i>Software developers*; ontology tools developer*; ontology developer*; web developer*</i>	<i>Project leaders*</i>	<i>Curators*</i>	<i>Ontology developers*; semantic data engineer*</i>
SAREF	<i>ETSI SmartM2M Technical Committee</i>	<i>Expert*</i>	-	<i>Ontology developer; Steering board members</i>	<i>Technical board</i>	<i>Project leaders, Contributors</i>	<i>Steering board members</i>	<i>Project lead; ontology developer</i>
AGROVOC	<i>Core board</i>	<i>External experts, ontology editors</i>	<i>AGROVOC team (Communication support)</i>	<i>Core board</i>	<i>Technical Board members</i>	<i>Editors</i>	<i>Agrovoc team (curator); experts</i>	<i>Editors: AGROVOC team (Technical support and manager)</i>

Appendix E. Alignment of BASF and OBO Principles

BASF principles ⁴⁹	OBO Foundry principles ⁵⁰
<p>P2) Availability - The latest ontology release MUST be discoverable through a lookup service and published in an ontology consumption platform where it is available to humans and machines alike, via APIs, direct access to the code, a SPARQL endpoint, or through an ontology visualization interface.</p> <p>P3) Access rights and security policy - Every BASF ontology MUST be accessible according to roles, confidentiality levels, access rights and security policies put in place in an access layer that implements the authorization procedures.</p>	<p>P1) Open - The ontology MUST be openly available to be used by all without any constraint other than (a) its origin must be acknowledged and (b) it is not to be altered and subsequently redistributed in altered form under the original name or with the same identifiers.</p>
<p>P4) Persistency - Ontologies are expected to change over time as they are developed, used, and refined. This will lead to a series of different versions of the ontology that MUST be persistent and accessible through a version control system.</p>	<p>P4) Versioning - The ontology provider has documented procedures for versioning the ontology and different versions of ontology are marked, stored, and officially released.</p> <p>P16) Maintenance - The ontology needs to reflect changes in scientific consensus to remain accurate over time.</p>
<p>P5) Documentation - Human-readable documentation MUST be included in BASF ontologies to provide context, descriptions and examples.</p>	<p>P8) Documentation - The ontology owners should strive to provide as much documentation as possible.</p>
<p>P1) Findability (F1) - (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.</p>	<p>P3) URI/Identifier Space - Each ontology MUST have a unique IRI in the form of an OBO Foundry permanent URL (PURL).</p>
<p>P1) Findability (F2) - data are described with rich ontology metadata.</p>	
<p>P1) Findability (F3) - (meta)data clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe.</p>	
<p>P1) Findability (F4) - are registered or indexed in a searchable resource, typically a repository.</p>	
<p>P1) Accessibility (A1) - (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol</p>	
<p>P1) Accessibility (A2) - metadata are accessible, even when the SA are no longer available</p>	
<p>P1) Interoperability (I1) - (meta)data uses a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.</p>	<p>P2) Common Format - The ontology is available in a common formal language in an accepted concrete syntax.</p>

⁴⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7007495>

⁵⁰ <https://obofoundry.org/principles/fp-000-summary.html>

P1) Interoperability (I2) - (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	
P1) Interoperability (I3) - (meta)data qualified references to other (meta)data	P7) Relations - Relations should be reused from the Relations Ontology (RO).
P1) Reusability (R1) - (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.	P6) Textual Definitions - The ontology has textual definitions for most classes and particular top-level terms. P9) Documented Plurality of Users - The ontology developers should document that multiple independent people or organisations use the ontology.
P6) Modularity - BASF ontologies SHOULD be modularized so that interconnected modules addressing specific knowledge areas in the scope of the ontology or having different security requirements, are networked in a usable way.	
P7) Community - The ontology development lifecycle is divided into several stages that involve different tasks. Multiple actors within the organization that constitute the ontology community play different roles during the ontology development process and have different degrees of involvement in its development tasks.	P11) Locus of Authority - There should be a person who is responsible for communications between the community and the ontology developers, for communicating with the Foundry on all Foundry-related matters, for mediating discussions involving maintenance in the light of scientific advance, and for ensuring that all user feedback is addressed.
	P12) Naming Conventions - The names (primary labels) for elements (classes, properties, etc.) in an ontology must be intelligible to scientists and amenable to natural language processing. Primary labels should be unique among OBO Library ontologies.
	P5) Scope - The scope of an ontology is the extent of the domain or subject matter it intends to cover. The ontology must have a specified scope and content that adheres to that scope.
	P10) Commitment To Collaboration —OBO Foundry ontology development should be carried out collaboratively, as with many other standards-oriented scientific activities.
	P13) Notification of Changes - Ontologies SHOULD announce significant changes to relevant stakeholders and collaborators before release.
	P20) Responsiveness - Ontology developers MUST offer channels for community participation and SHOULD be responsive to requests.